

Vacuum frying as an alternative technique to increase the oxidative stability of sunflower oil. A comprehensive ^1H NMR and SPME-GC/MS study focused on oxygenated compounds

Andrea Martinez-Yusta, Ainhoa Ruiz-Aracama, Jon Alberdi-Cedeño*

Food Technology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Lascaray Research Center, University of the Basque Country (UPV-EHU), Paseo de la Universidad n° 7, 01006, Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain

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ABSTRACT

The present study compares the oxidative stability of sunflower oil during vacuum frying (120 °C, low pressure) and conventional frying (170 °C, atmospheric pressure), focusing on the formation of oxygenated oxidation products. To discern between the effects of temperature and reduced concentration of oxygen during vacuum frying, the stability of sunflower oil under atmospheric frying conditions at 120 °C was also evaluated. Oil samples were analysed using Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H NMR) and Solid Phase Microextraction (SPME) followed by Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS). Additionally, the percentage of Total Polar Compounds (TPC) and the viscosity were determined. Under vacuum frying conditions, the degradation rate of linoleate was slower than under atmospheric frying conditions. Likewise, the formation of different oxygenated oxidation compounds, including monohydroperoxy- monohydroxy- and monoketo-conjugated-octadecadienoates, Z-monoepoxy-Z-octadecenoates and aldehydes, some of which are potentially harmful, was also delayed. Similarly, the evolution of the TPC percentage and viscosity changes showed a slower rate. These results provide, for the first time, a comprehensive understanding of the effect of vacuum frying on the stability of sunflower oil, highlighting its potential as a promising alternative to conventional frying methods.

1. Introduction

Frying is a culinary process used worldwide, both industrially and domestically, in which food is immersed in oil at high temperatures. Although fried foods are highly appreciated for their organoleptic characteristics, the high temperatures involved in this process and the possible presence of water from the food cause degradation of the oil through thermooxidation, hydrolysis and polymerisation reactions, among others (Marmesat et al., 2008; Abrante-Pascual et al., 2024). Therefore, it is crucial to find ways to improve the oxidative stability of oils used in frying. Some strategies adopted by the Food Industry include enriching frying oils with compounds with potential antioxidant activity (Márquez-Ruiz et al., 2014), as well as exploring alternative frying techniques, such as pressure, microwave, radiant and vacuum frying, among others (Pankaj & Keener, 2017; Devi et al., 2021). However, to date, only vacuum frying has gained acceptance and has been used commercially by the food industries (Pankaj & Keener, 2017). In this technique, the application of pressure below atmospheric levels reduces

the boiling point of water, thus minimising the frying temperature of the oil (Manzoor et al., 2022; Pankaj & Keener, 2017). The combination of the lower temperature and the lower amount of oxygen during vacuum frying improves the quality characteristics of fried foods and could contribute to improved oxidative stability of oils.

In this context, several studies have compared the effects of vacuum frying and conventional frying, with and without food, on the oxidative stability of lard and various vegetable oils, such as rice bran, soybean, rapeseed, canola, mustard, palm, sunflower, high-oleic sunflower and high-oleic acid content oils. These experiments were carried out at temperatures between 100 °C and 130 °C for vacuum frying and between 145 °C and 180 °C for conventional frying (Albertos et al., 2016; Basuny et al., 2012; Belkova et al., 2018; Crosa et al., 2014; Manzoor et al., 2022; Nateghi et al., 2018; Pandey et al., 2022; Yamsaengsung et al., 2017; Yousef & Nateghi, 2012). In general, the results of these experiments showed that different reactions, such as oxidation, polymerisation and hydrolysis, occurred during vacuum frying to a lesser extent and at a slower rate than in atmospheric frying. However, it

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: jon.alberdi@ehu.eus (J. Alberdi-Cedeño).

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should be noted that in most of these studies, the oxidative stability of the oils was measured using classical methods such as changes in colour, viscosity, Peroxide Value, *p*-Anisidine Value, Carbonyl Value, Thio-barbituric Acid test (TBA), Acid Value, Iodine Value, Refraction index, and Total Polar Compounds (TPC), among others. These methods only provide information on certain compounds or functional groups and do not give details on the specific nature of the compounds involved in each determination, which could sometimes lead to incomplete or inaccurate conclusions.

Similarly, studies focused on the determination of specific secondary oxidation compounds generated during vacuum frying, such as aldehydes, are scarce, and only a few of them have been determined (Belkova et al., 2018). In this regard, it is well known that under frying conditions these secondary oxidation compounds are formed (Han & Csallany, 2008; Guillén & Uriarte, 2009, 2012a, 2012b, 2012c, 2012d; Gerde et al., 2011), and some of them have been described as potentially toxic, including oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes (Esterbauer et al., 1991; Guillén & Goicoechea, 2008). Although the oxygen concentration is low under vacuum frying conditions, these potentially toxic oxygenated aldehydes, derived from the degradation of polyunsaturated acyl groups, can still be formed.

Currently, there are no studies that address in depth the changes undergone by oils subjected to vacuum frying conditions, exploring the nature of the oxidation compounds generated, in particular the potentially harmful ones.

In this context, the present study aimed to investigate the effect of vacuum frying conditions (120 °C at low pressure) compared to conventional frying (170 °C at atmospheric pressure) on the oxidative stability of sunflower oil. In addition, to discern between the influence of temperature and the effect of the reduction of oxygen concentration during vacuum frying due to air removal, the evolution of sunflower oil under atmospheric frying conditions at 120 °C was also studied. Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (^1H NMR) and Solid Phase Microextraction (SPME) followed by Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (GC/MS) were used to study the oil samples in a comprehensive manner. These techniques provide a large amount of information without chemical modification of the sample and in a simple way. Furthermore, and in parallel, viscosity and the percentage of Total Polar Compounds (TPC) were determined. The determination of TPC was carried out to establish the end-point of the experiments, since in Spain and other European countries, the 25% TPC limit is the legal threshold for frying oils (Hwang et al., 2020).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

The oil used in the present study was refined sunflower oil from the same batch, purchased from a local oil supplier. Its original composition, expressed as the molar percentage of acyl groups, was as follows: 56.8 ± 0.3 for linoleic groups, 30.8 ± 0.4 for oleic and 12.4 ± 0.0 for saturated acyl groups. These percentages were determined by ^1H NMR, as described in previous studies (Guillén & Ruiz, 2003; Guillén & Uriarte, 2009).

2.2. Oil heating experiments

2.2.1. Vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF)

Three litres of sunflower oil were heated at 120 ± 5 °C in a 10 L vacuum fryer (model 20000, Gastrovac) for 6 h/day cycles, breaking the vacuum every hour according to the manufacturer's specifications. The dimensions of the stainless steel fryer vessel were 47 cm wide x 47 cm long x 40 cm high. Throughout the heating process, the oil was not replenished and was kept at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C) between heating episodes. Oil samples were periodically collected and, when necessary, frozen until analysis. During the entire heating period, the oil

was not replenished and, as a result of sampling, the total volume of heated oil extracted amounted to almost 174 mL. The experiment was carried out in duplicate and ended when the percentage of TPC in the oil reached 25% (162 h in total), which is the legal limit for the use of frying oils in Spain and some other European countries.

2.2.2. Atmospheric frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF)

To compare the oxidative stability of the oil under vacuum-frying conditions with that under conventional atmospheric frying, 3 L of sunflower oil were heated to 170 ± 5 °C in a stainless steel tank (47 cm wide x 47 cm long x 40 cm high), which matched the dimensions of the vacuum fryer. Since the stainless steel tank had no probe, the oil temperature was constantly monitored using a Testo 175-T3 temperature recorder (Testo SE & Co. KGaA, Leizkirch, Germany). Samples were collected periodically, as previously described, until the oil reached 25% TPC (30 h in total). The total volume of heated oil extracted amounted to almost 36 mL. The experiment was carried out in duplicate.

2.2.3. Atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF)

To study the effect of the reduced oxygen concentration during vacuum-frying and to exclude the influence of temperature, a third experiment was conducted. For this, 3 L of sunflower oil were heated to the same temperature as in the vacuum-frying conditions (120 ± 5 °C), but using the same stainless steel tank used for the atmospheric frying experiments at 170 °C. The temperature of the oil was also constantly monitored using a Testo 175-T3 temperature recorder (Testo SE & Co. KGaA, Leizkirch, Germany). Samples were collected as described above until the oil reached 25% TPC (44 h in total). Overall, the total volume of heated oil extracted amounted to almost 54 mL. The experiment was carried out in duplicate.

2.3. Monitoring by ^1H NMR

2.3.1. Operating conditions

The evolution of the sunflower oil subjected to the aforementioned frying conditions was monitored by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. The analysis was performed using a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz, as in previous work (Guillén & Ruiz, 2003). For sample preparation, 175 μl of oil were mixed in a 5 mm diameter ^1H NMR tube with 425 μl of deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3 , 99.8%), which contained 0.03% tetramethylsilane (TMS) as an internal reference. In order to select the most appropriate values to obtain accurate quantitative results in the shortest possible period of time, a very broad range of recycling times and relaxation delays were tested in the acquisition of the ^1H NMR spectra. Thus, the acquisition parameters were as follows: spectral width of 6250 Hz, relaxation delay of 3 s, number of scans 64, acquisition time of 2.621 s and, and pulse width of 90°, resulting in a total acquisition time of 6 min 20 s. The relaxation delay and acquisition time allow the complete relaxation of the protons. The ^1H NMR spectra obtained were processed using MestreNova program (Mestrelab Research, Santiago de Compostela, Spain).

2.3.2. Identification and quantification from ^1H NMR spectral data

The identification of the compounds present in the oil, as well as of those generated during the different heating processes, was performed based on the assignment of ^1H NMR signals corresponding to the hydrogen atoms of different structures, as described in previous studies (Guillén & Ruiz, 2003; Guillén & Ruiz, 2005a,b,c; Goicoechea & Guillén, 2010; Martínez-Yusta et al., 2014; Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2020), and/or by using standards.

The concentrations of linoleic acyl groups and various oxidation products present in the samples was possible because the areas of the ^1H NMR signals are proportional to the number of protons responsible for each signal. Thus, the concentration of linoleic acyl groups, expressed as a molar percentage (%), and the content of the different oxidation products (OP), given in millimoles per mol of triglyceride (mmol/mol

TG), were determined using the equations S1 and S2, along with the corresponding signals from Table S1 (see Supplementary Material).

2.4. Monitoring of volatile aldehydes by SPME-GC/MS

Solid Phase Microextraction (SPME). The extraction of the volatile components from the headspace of the samples under study (0.5 g of oil in 10 mL screw-cap vial) was performed automatically using a CombiPAL autosampler (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The fibre used was coated with DVB/CAR/PDMS (Divinylbenzene/Carboxen/Polydimethylsiloxane, 50/30 μm film thickness, 1 cm length), acquired from Supelco (Sigma-Aldrich). This fibre was inserted into the headspace of the sample and maintained for 60 min at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Variables such as the type of fibre (polarity and thickness of the coating) and the extraction conditions (sample and headspace volumes, extraction time and temperature) had previously been optimised in our laboratory to select the best extraction conditions. The effectiveness of the SPME fibre used was periodically verified by testing its extraction efficiency and repeatability with a reference sample of known composition.

Gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (GC/MS) study. The chromatographic run was executed according to previous studies (Guillén et al., 2005). Briefly, the fibre containing the extracted components was desorbed for 10 min in the injection port (splitless mode with a 5-min purge time) of a gas chromatograph model GC 7890A equipped with a mass selective detector 5975C inert MSD with Triple Axis Detector (Agilent Technologies) and a computer operating with the ChemStation program. The column used was a fused-silica capillary column (60 m long x 0.25 mm inner diameter x 0.25 μm film thickness, from Agilent J & W Advanced Capillary GC Columns), coated with a non-polar stationary phase (HP-5MS, 5% phenyl methyl siloxane). The operating conditions were as follows: the oven temperature was initially set at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5 min hold), increased to 290 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ (2 min hold); the temperatures of the ion source and the quadrupole mass analyser were maintained at 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively; helium was used as the carrier gas at a pressure of 18.611 psi and a linear flow velocity of 1 mL/min; the injector temperature was held at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; mass spectra were recorded at an ionisation energy of 70 eV; and the data acquisition mode employed was Scan. Following the initial desorption, the fibre was routinely re-exposed to desorption conditions for cleaning and to verify the completeness of the first process. To prevent contamination between runs, the fibre was subjected to a 20 min bake-out at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the Fibre Cleaning and Conditioning Station of the CombiPAL autosampler.

Most of the components were identified using commercial standards (asterisked compounds in Table 1) acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). When standards were not available, identification was based on matching the mass spectra with those from scientific literature or from a commercial library with a match greater than 85% (Wiley W9N08, Mass Spectral Database of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)). The semiquantification of the compounds was based on the area counts of the base peak (Bp) in the mass spectrum of each compound, divided by 10^6 . When the Bp of a compound overlapped with the corresponding ion peak in the mass spectrum of another compound, an alternative ion peak was selected for the quantification of the former. Although the chromatographic response factor varies for each compound, the area counts thus determined are useful for the comparison of the abundance of each compound across samples. Compounds with abundance values lower than 50,000 area counts were considered traces.

2.5. Determination of the percentage of Total Polar Compounds (TPC) and viscosity

The percentage of TPC was determined during the entire heating process using a Testo 270 instrument (Testo, Lenzkirch, Germany) by direct immersion in the oil. This instrument determines the dielectric constant of the oil, and it directly transforms these values into TPC. As

indicated above, the measurements were carried out in duplicate until the oil reached 25% TPC, which represents the maximum permissible limit for heated fats and oils in many European countries (Hwang et al., 2020). Exceeding this threshold requires oil replacement. To measure the viscosity, a Visco Star + L viscometer (Visco Star Plus L, Fungilab, Barcelona, Spain) was used. Briefly, 500 ml of oil at a constant temperature (20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) was placed in a 600 ml beaker, and the spindle was immersed in the oil with a shear rate of 200 rpm until the value obtained remained constant.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The data in the figures and tables represent mean values from two independent determinations. The values shown graphically correspond to the averages together with error bars. The significance of the differences of the various compounds among samples (Figs. 1–6 and Table 1) was assessed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's b test at $p < 0.05$, together with the Student's t-test at $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS Statistics v.28 software (IBM, NY, USA).

3. Results and discussion

Throughout various heating processes, sunflower oil underwent thermodegradation. In all cases, this process involved the degradation of its most unsaturated acyl groups (linoleic), leading to the formation of different oxidation compounds. It is well-known that the evolution of these compounds during thermodegradation depends fundamentally on the composition of the oil, both in major and minor components, and on the processing conditions applied. The latter include the heat transfer mechanisms (convection, conduction, and infrared or microwave radiation), heating temperature, heating time and the amount of oxygen present, among other factors (Martínez-Yusta et al., 2014). Considering these variables, and given that the same oil was used in all experiments (120VF, 120AF and 170AF), the differences observed in its evolution under frying conditions can be attributed solely to the processing parameters.

3.1. Evolution of linoleic acyl groups

Fig. 1 depicts the diminution in the molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups over heating time (hours) for the three experiments. In all cases (120VF, 120AF and 170AF), the decrease in linoleic molar percentage over time fitted with a high correlation coefficient to linear equations,

Fig. 1. Evolution of the molar percentage of linoleic acyl groups in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (120VF \circ - \circ), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (120AF Δ - Δ) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (170AF \times - \times). For the same heating time, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between samples are asterisked (*) and grouped in dotted squares.

which are also given in Fig. 1. It can be seen that temperature had a clear effect on the evolution of the linoleic acyl groups, since the degradation rate under atmospheric frying conditions at 170 °C (-0.3109 M percentage hour⁻¹) was approximately twice as fast as under atmospheric frying conditions at 120 °C (-0.1644 M percentage hour⁻¹) (see 170AF vs 120AF in Fig. 1). As for the sample subjected to vacuum frying conditions, it is worth mentioning that the reduced oxygen concentration near the oil had a more pronounced effect than the heating temperature itself. Specifically, the degradation rate of linoleic acyl groups under vacuum conditions was approximately four times slower (-0.0445 M percentage hour⁻¹) than at the same temperature under atmospheric conditions (see 120VF vs 120AF).

As expected, the combination of lower processing temperature and lower oxygen concentration in the medium (120VF vs 170AF) resulted in a seven-fold slower degradation rate, demonstrating that vacuum frying could serve as a valuable strategy to improve the oxidative stability of the oil. The results concerning the evolution of linoleic acyl groups are in agreement with those of Manzoor et al. (2022), who reported a lower degradation of polyunsaturated fatty acids (linoleic and linolenic) in soybean oil during vacuum frying of potato chips compared to conventional frying.

3.2. Evolution of oxidation compounds

As mentioned above, the degradation of the main oil components leads to the formation of new derived compounds. In the present study, special attention was paid to various oxygenated oxidation products, which include structures with different functional groups such as hydroperoxy, hydroxy, keto, epoxy and aldehyde.

3.2.1. Monohydroperoxy conjugated-octadecadienoates

It is well known that the first compounds formed as a result of the oxidation of unsaturated acyl chains are those containing hydroperoxide functional groups, exhibiting conjugated diene structures with either (*Z*, *E*)- or (*E*,*E*)-isomers. During the thermo-degradation process at temperatures above 100 °C, monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*-octadecadienoates are unstable and isomerise into monohydroperoxy conjugated-*E*,*E*-octadecadienoates (Schneider, 2009). It is important to note that the fresh oil used in these experiments contained a small concentration of the (*Z*,*E*)-isomer (0.92 ± 0.14 mmol/mol TG), suggesting that the fresh oil had undergone minimal oxidation prior to the experiment.

Fig. 2 plots the evolution of the concentrations of monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*- and -*E*,*E*-octadecadienoates over heating time under different frying conditions. As shown in this figure, there are clear differences in the evolution of these primary oxidation products among the experiments. Under atmospheric frying conditions at 170 °C, the concentration of monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*-octadecadienoates was very low, remaining practically stable below 1 mmol/mol TG throughout the heating process, until the oils reached 25% TPC after 30 h (see 170AF in Fig. 2a). In this oil sample, the (*E*,*E*)-isomer was not detected. This observation can be attributed to the high temperature (170 °C), as hydroperoxides degrade at high speed at elevated temperatures, which prevents significant accumulation and causes them to rapidly evolve to other oxidation compounds (Martínez-Yusta et al., 2014). These results are in agreement with previous studies performed on vegetable oils heated to frying temperatures, where monohydroperoxy conjugated-octadecadienoates were either not detected (Guillén & Uriarte, 2012a, 2012b, 2012c) or were only found at very low concentrations at the beginning of the experiment (Wu et al., 2021). In contrast, under atmospheric pressure at the lower temperature of 120 °C, monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*-octadecadienoates were generated to a greater extent, with concentrations approximately four times higher than those observed at 170 °C (Fig. 2a). Moreover, after the first frying cycle (6 h), monohydroperoxy conjugated-*E*,*E*-octadecadienoates were also detected (Fig. 2b). From this point on, the

Fig. 2. Evolution of the concentration in millimol per mol of triglyceride of a) monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*-octadecadienoates and b) monohydroperoxy conjugated-*E*,*E*-octadecadienoates detected in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF -o-), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF -Δ-) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF -x-). For the same heating time, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between samples are asterisked (*) and grouped in dotted squares.

concentration of (*Z*,*E*)-isomers progressively decreased, while that of (*E*, *E*) increased, reaching values of approximately 13 mmol/mol TG by the end of the process (see 120AF). As for the vacuum frying experiment (120VF), both *Z*,*E* and *E*,*E*-isomers were identified, with concentration values between those observed in the 120AF and 170AF experiments. As in the 120AF experiment, under vacuum frying conditions, the concentration of monohydroperoxy conjugated-(*E*,*E*)-octadecadienoates was also higher than that of (*Z*,*E*)-isomers, indicating that the reduced oxygen level at 120 °C did not modify the formation pathway of hydroperoxides, but did influence the concentration they reached.

Taken together, these data reveal that the formation and evolution of monohydroperoxy conjugated-octadecadienoates are strongly determined by both the processing temperature and the oxygen content in the vicinity of the oil. Specifically, the higher the temperature and the lower the oxygen content, the lower the formation of these compounds.

3.2.2. Monohydroxy conjugated-octadecadienoates

In all three samples (120VF, 120AF and 170AF), only monohydroxy conjugated-*Z*,*E*-octadecadienoates were detected, and the evolution of their concentration over time is shown in Fig. 3. Under atmospheric conditions, these compounds were formed from the beginning of the process, their evolution at 120 °C and 170 °C being almost identical. In both cases, the rate of formation was approximately 0.06 mmol/mol TG per hour (see 120AF and 170AF in Fig. 3). This suggests that, under atmospheric conditions, temperature has no direct impact on the

Fig. 3. Evolution of the concentration in millimol per mol of triglyceride of monohydroxy conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates detected in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF -○-), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF -Δ-) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF -x-). For the same heating time, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between samples are asterisked (*) and grouped in dotted squares.

formation of these compounds. However, under vacuum frying conditions, the formation of monohydroxy conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates was delayed compared to atmospheric frying, being detected only after 18 h of heating (see 120VF in Fig. 3). This indicates that a lower content of oxygen has a clear effect on the formation of these oxidation products. Notably, although the formation of these compounds has been previously described during accelerated storage processes of corn, sunflower and walnut oils (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2020; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022; Morales et al., 2012), as well as in sunflower oil subjected to frying temperatures (180 °C) (Marmesat et al., 2008), no study has yet reported their formation under vacuum frying conditions.

Monohydroxy conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates have been described as arising from the direct oxidation of linoleic acyl groups or from the reduction of monohydroperoxy conjugated-octadecadienoates (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2020). However, considering the low oxygen concentration under vacuum frying conditions, it could be postulated that the reduction of monohydroperoxy conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates is the predominant pathway for the formation of monohydroxy conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates, in contrast to what may occur under higher oxygen concentrations.

3.2.3. Monoketo conjugated-octadecadienoates

Z,E- and *E,E*-conjugated double bonds associated with monoketo conjugated-octadecadienoates derived from oxidised linoleic acyl groups were also detected in the studied samples, and their evolution is shown in Fig. 4. It can be observed that both the formation and evolution of monoketo conjugated-*Z,E*- and -*E,E*-octadecadienoates were affected by temperature and oxygen content. In particular, the (*Z,E*)-isomer was only found at 120 °C, both under atmospheric (120AF) and vacuum (120VF) conditions, although with a slightly different behaviour. Indeed, under vacuum frying conditions, the (*Z,E*)-isomer was formed later (after 24 h of heating) than at atmospheric pressure (after 18 h of heating). However, at the end of the experiment, when 25% TPC was reached in both samples, its concentration was more than twice as high under vacuum frying (162 h) than under atmospheric pressure (44 h), as shown in Fig. 4a.

On the other hand, monoketo conjugated-*E,E*-octadecadienoates were detected in all experiments. In samples 120AF and 170AF they were present from the beginning, showing the same formation rate in both (0.06 mmol/mol TG * hour). In contrast, in sample 120VF, these compounds were only detected after 18 h of heating, although once generated, their formation rate was similar to that observed in 120AF and 170AF experiments (see Fig. 4b). As for the monoketo conjugated-*Z*,

Fig. 4. Evolution of the concentration in millimol per mol of triglyceride of a) monoketo conjugated-*Z,E*-octadecadienoates and b) monoketo conjugated-*E,E*-octadecadienoates detected in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF -○-), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF -Δ-) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF -x-). For the same heating time, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between samples are asterisked (*) and grouped in dotted squares.

E-octadecadienoates, the concentration of (*E,E*)-isomers reached at the end of the experiment under vacuum frying conditions (after 162 h) was more than twice as high as in both atmospheric conditions, which reached 25% TPC at 30 h in the case of 170AF and 44 h in the case of 120AF. The higher concentrations of both monoketo-conjugated isomers under vacuum frying conditions could be explained by the longer heating process and the oxygen still present in the medium (as evidenced by the formation of other oxidation compounds, such as monohydroperoxy dienes). Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the concentration of monoketo conjugated-*E,E*-octadecadienoates was more than two times higher than that of the *Z,E*-isomers in all heating processes (170AF, 120AF and 120VF). The generation of higher concentrations of monoketo conjugated-*E,E*-octadecadienoates compared to (*Z,E*)-isomers has been previously described during peroxidation of human serum albumin (HSA)-bound linoleic acid (Dufour & Loonis, 2005), oxidation of corn oil under accelerated storage conditions (Alberdi-Cedeño et al., 2020), and in soybean oil during frying (Wu et al., 2021). However, to our knowledge, no studies have investigated the formation and evolution of these compounds under vacuum frying conditions. Some authors have suggested that ketodieneic compounds could be derived from the reduction of hydroperoxides of linoleic acyl groups (Kuklev et al., 1997) as well as from the oxidation of hydroxy-conjugated-dienes (Iacazio, 2003). However, considering the limited oxygen availability during vacuum frying conditions, it could be hypothesised that monoketo conjugated-octadecadienoates are generated predominantly through the

reduction of hydroperoxy conjugated-octadecadienoates, rather than from the oxidation of hydroxy conjugated-octadecadienoates.

3.2.4. Epoxides

In relation to acyl chains containing epoxy functional groups, only *Z*-monoepoxy-*Z*-octadecenoates were detected. These compounds were found in samples 170AF, 120AF and 120VF after 12, 18 and 102 h, respectively. The samples subjected to atmospheric conditions (170AF and 120AF) reached higher maximum concentrations (around 8 mmol/mol TG) at the end of the experiment, compared to those exposed to vacuum frying, which reached concentrations of around 5 mmol/mol TG, as shown in Fig. 5. The present study therefore demonstrates that the rate of formation of *Z*-monoepoxy-*Z*-monoenes depends on the heating temperature, so that the higher the temperature, the earlier they are formed. However, and to a greater extent, their formation also depends on the oxygen concentration in the oil headspace, so that the lower the oxygen concentration, the later they form and at significantly lower concentrations. Multiple pathways for the formation of epoxides have been described (Schaich, 2023). However, since only *Z*-monoepoxy-*Z*-monoenes were detected in the samples from the three different experiments (170AF, 120AF and 120VF), the most likely route of formation would be the addition of lipid peroxy radical (LOO[•]) directly to the linoleic double bond (Schaich, 2023), since the *Z*-isomerisation of the double bond is preserved in the epoxy group formed. Previous studies in sunflower oil heated at 70 °C, 100 °C and 180 °C under atmospheric conditions have reported the formation of *Z*-monoepoxy-*Z*-monoenes (Velasco et al., 2004; Marmesat et al., 2008; Goicoechea & Guillen, 2010; Caño-Ochoa et al., 2022). However, to date, no study has addressed the formation of epoxides under vacuum frying conditions.

3.2.5. Aldehydes

After subjecting sunflower oil to the different heating conditions, the types of aldehydes detected by ¹H NMR in all samples coincided with those previously reported when sunflower oil was subjected to frying temperatures (Guillén & Uriarte, 2009, 2012a): (*E,E*)-2,4-alkadienals, (*E*)-2-alkenals, *n*-alkanals, 4-hydroxy-(*E*)-2-alkenals, 4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-alkenals and (*Z,E*)-2,4-alkadienals. Furthermore, under atmospheric frying conditions at 170 °C, 4-oxo-alkanals were detected, which were not observed in the samples subjected to lower temperatures (120 AF and 120 VF) (see Fig. S1). To obtain more detailed information on the specific nature of the aldehydes formed in the three heating processes, SPME-GC/MS was carried out, as mentioned above. Table 1 shows the abundances of these aldehydes in the headspace of sunflower oil

subjected to vacuum frying (120VF) and atmospheric frying conditions (120AF and 170AF) at different time points. As can be seen in this table, the **alkanals** found ranged from 4 to 10 carbon atoms, and many of them were already present in the headspace of the fresh sunflower oil (see Supplementary Tables S2–S4). As the heating time progressed, the number and abundances of these aldehydes increased, with pentanal, hexanal and nonanal being the most abundant. However, their evolution varied depending on the heating conditions. After the first heating cycle (6 h), the lowest abundance of all alkanals was observed under vacuum frying conditions (120VF), followed by atmospheric frying at the same temperature (120AF). However, as the heating time progressed, the abundances of these aldehydes became increasingly similar in the two experiments, converging at 42 h, at the end of the 120AF experiment (see total alkanals in 120VF and 120AF). This suggests that the formation of these saturated aldehydes was not significantly influenced by the lower concentration of oxygen in the oil headspace. On the contrary, higher temperatures had a clear effect on the formation of alkanals. As shown in Table 1, Fig. S1, and Tables S2–S4, from the initial heating cycle to the end in the 170AF experiment (30 h), the abundances of these aldehydes were significantly higher than those observed at 120VF and 120AF conditions. This is in agreement with the study by Belkova et al. (2018), who reported lower concentrations of hexanal and nonanal in the headspace of rapeseed oil during vacuum frying of potatoes at 125 °C compared to atmospheric frying at 165 °C. Furthermore, (*E*)-2-alkenals were also detected in the headspace of the starting sunflower oil (see Tables S2–S4). After 6 h of heating, the abundances of these unsaturated aldehydes increased in all three experiments, with (*E*)-2-heptenal being the most abundant in each case (see Table 1 and Tables S2–S4). When comparing 120AF and 120VF, it can be observed that the limited oxygen concentration under vacuum significantly influenced the evolution of (*E*)-2-alkenals, such that they showed a lower formation rate throughout the process. Thus, for the same time points shown in Table 1, their abundances under vacuum frying were significantly lower than those under atmospheric frying conditions at the same temperature (see 120VF vs 120AF in Table 1). As for the effect of the heating temperature, it was found that higher temperatures accelerated the formation of (*E*)-2-alkenals. At 170AF, these compounds reached their maximum abundance after 18 h of heating, and subsequently their levels decreased, probably to give rise to the formation of other secondary or downstream oxidation compounds. These results align with those of Belkova et al. (2018), who observed a tenfold lower amount of 2-heptenal in the headspace of rapeseed oil during vacuum frying of potatoes than after frying at atmospheric pressure.

Other volatile aldehydes typically formed in the heating process of sunflower oil are 2,4-alkadienals (Guillén & Uriarte, 2012d). These kinds of aldehydes are more reactive than the previous two, and are therefore considered more toxic (Grootveld et al., 1998). As shown in Tables S2–S4, small amounts of 2,4-(*Z,E*)-decadienal and 2,4-(*E,E*)-decadienal were found in the headspace of the initial sunflower oil. After heating, regardless of the conditions, both 2,4-(*Z,E*)- and -(*E,E*)-decadienals were generated in highest abundance throughout the heating processes, particularly the (*E,E*)-isomer, as shown in Table 1. Furthermore, other 2,4-alkadienals, such as those with 7, 8, 9 and 11 carbon atoms, were also detected during the different experiments. It should be noted that the abundance of 2,4-alkadienals increased throughout the process in both 120AF and 120VF experiments, while in 170AF, they reached the maximum abundance at 18 h, decreasing thereafter, probably because they were transformed into further oxidation products. Again, the formation rate of these diunsaturated aldehydes was slower under vacuum frying (120VF) compared to atmospheric conditions (Tables S2–S4). Thus, after the first frying cycle (6 h), the total abundance of 2,4-alkadienals was three times lower at 120VF than at 120AF, and 15 times lower than at 170AF (see Table 1). Furthermore, after 30 h (170AF) and 42 h (120AF), the end point of both experiments, the abundance of these type of aldehydes remained significantly lower in the vacuum frying experiment (120VF).

Fig. 5. Evolution of the concentration in millimol per mol of triglyceride of *Z*-monoepoxy-*Z*-octadecenoates detected in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF -o-), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF -Δ-) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF -x-).

Table 1

Volatile aldehydes identified by SPME-GC/MS in the headspace of sunflower oil samples submitted to different heating experiments over different periods of time (hours). Data are expressed as area counts of their mass spectra base peak (Bp) divided by 10^6 . Different letters within each row for each experiment time indicate a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the heating conditions.

Compound (molecular weight)	Bp	6h			18h			30h			42h	
		120VF	120AF	170AF	120VF	120AF	170AF	120VF	120AF	170AF	120 VF	120AF
<i>Alkanals</i>												
Butanal (72)*	44	0.2 ± 0.0a	0.2 ± 0.0a	0.2 ± 0.1a	0.3 ± 0.1a	0.3 ± 0.0a	0.4 ± 0.0a	0.3 ± 0.1a	0.5 ± 0.0a	0.4 ± 0.2a	0.3 ± 0.0a	0.5 ± 0.2a
Pentanal (86)*	43	4.9 ± 0.1c	5.4 ± 0.0b	5.8 ± 0.0a	7.6 ± 0.3a	6.7 ± 0.1 ab	6.1 ± 0.4b	6.9 ± 0.1a	7.3 ± 0.4a	5.8 ± 0.6a	5.6 ± 0.8b	7.1 ± 0.0a
Hexanal (100)*	44	27.0 ± 0.2c	38.2 ± 0.9b	48.6 ± 0.2a	58.9 ± 2.9a	37.0 ± 0.3b	51.0 ± 2.7a	55.4 ± 8.1a	42.5 ± 3.3a	48.0 ± 5.1a	40.6 ± 5.7a	43.3 ± 0.1a
Heptanal (114)*	70	1.2 ± 0.0c	2.5 ± 0.1b	6.7 ± 0.1a	4.0 ± 0.1a	3.9 ± 0.1a	3.9 ± 0.1a	5.4 ± 0.9b	4.6 ± 0.1b	7.5 ± 0.6a	4.9 ± 0.3a	4.3 ± 0.1a
Octanal (128)*	41	2.1 ± 0.4b	2.6 ± 0.5b	4.5 ± 0.2a	3.1 ± 0.1c	3.8 ± 0.0b	6.7 ± 0.1a	2.9 ± 0.1b	3.7 ± 0.5b	6.6 ± 0.2a	3.7 ± 0.0a	3.8 ± 0.4a
Nonanal (142)*	57	1.8 ± 0.0c	13.2 ± 0.7b	26.5 ± 0.8a	7.0 ± 0.1c	26.2 ± 0.6b	42.9 ± 1.1a	10.2 ± 0.0c	14.8 ± 1.1b	32.9 ± 1.3a	13.9 ± 1.5a	10.1 ± 0.3a
Decanal (156)*	57	–	–	0.2 ± 0.0	–	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.5 ± 0.0a	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.5 ± 0.0a	0.1 ± 0.0a	0.1 ± 0.0a
Total		37.1 ± 0.8c	62.2 ± 0.4b	92.5 ± 1.2a	80.9 ± 3.2b	77.9 ± 0.9b	111.5 ± 4.2a	81.1 ± 9.2 ab	73.6 ± 3.3b	101.8 ± 5.5a	69.1 ± 5.3a	69.2 ± 0.1a
<i>(E)-2-Alkenals</i>												
(E)-2-Butenal (70)*	70	0.7 ± 0.0a	0.7 ± 0.1a	0.8 ± 0.0a	0.8 ± 0.0a	0.7 ± 0.2a	1.0 ± 0.2a	1.1 ± 0.4a	0.8 ± 0.2a	1.4 ± 0.5a	0.3 ± 0.1b	1.3 ± 0.1a
(E)-2-Hexenal (98)	41	4.0 ± 0.2c	7.3 ± 0.5b	18.5 ± 0.0a	11.1 ± 2.7b	14.4 ± 0.2 ab	20.3 ± 0.7a	16.8 ± 1.0a	17.3 ± 0.8a	16.1 ± 1.2a	15.6 ± 1.1a	13.5 ± 0.4a
(E)-2-Heptenal (112)*	41	31.0 ± 1.2c	66.7 ± 0.9b	175.0 ± 3.0a	94.1 ± 5.2c	135.2 ± 0.2b	205.8 ± 4.2a	140.1 ± 0.7b	163.4 ± 2.0a	163.9 ± 2.3a	161.0 ± 0.0b	148.8 ± 2.2a
(E)-2-Octenal (126)*	70	1.0 ± 0.1c	3.3 ± 0.1b	15.1 ± 0.4a	6.0 ± 0.4c	19.3 ± 0.2b	34.1 ± 0.6a	12.2 ± 1.4b	28.7 ± 1.8a	28.6 ± 2.1a	20.2 ± 1.4b	32.0 ± 0.0a
(E)-2-Nonenal (140)*	55	0.2 ± 0.0c	0.5 ± 0.0b	1.6 ± 0.0a	0.7 ± 0.0c	2.2 ± 0.0b	4.0 ± 0.0a	1.1 ± 0.0b	3.6 ± 0.2a	3.6 ± 0.2a	1.8 ± 0.1b	4.1 ± 0.0a
(E)-2-Decenal (154)*	70	–	0.5 ± 0.0b	7.7 ± 0.7a	1.0 ± 0.0c	4.3 ± 0.3b	18.7 ± 1.0a	2.3 ± 0.1c	10.1 ± 1.0b	15.2 ± 1.0a	5.2 ± 1.0b	14.2 ± 0.1a
(E)-2-Undecenal (168)*	70	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.2 ± 0.0b	3.4 ± 0.3a	0.4 ± 0.1c	2.0 ± 0.3b	9.9 ± 0.5a	1.0 ± 0.1c	5.2 ± 0.5b	9.6 ± 1.1a	2.5 ± 0.8b	8.1 ± 0.2a
Total		37.1 ± 1.6c	79.2 ± 0.7b	222.2 ± 4.4a	114.1 ± 8.3c	178.2 ± 0.7b	293.9 ± 6.8a	174.6 ± 0.8b	229.2 ± 4.9a	238.4 ± 1.5a	206.6 ± 2.2b	222.0 ± 2.2a
<i>2,4-Alkadienals</i>												
(Z,E)-2,4-Heptadienal (110)	81	0.9 ± 0.2b	1.2 ± 0.7b	5.3 ± 0.7a	2.6 ± 0.1c	4.1 ± 0.0b	6.4 ± 0.8a	3.5 ± 0.3a	4.1 ± 0.1a	4.3 ± 0.4a	5.0 ± 0.2a	3.3 ± 0.0b
(E,E)-2,4-Heptadienal (110)*	81	0.8 ± 0.1c	2.2 ± 0.5b	4.4 ± 0.0a	2.4 ± 0.4b	3.6 ± 0.3b	5.8 ± 0.5a	3.3 ± 0.9a	3.4 ± 0.0a	3.6 ± 0.0a	5.3 ± 0.0a	2.7 ± 0.1b
(E,E)-2,4-Octadienal (124)	81	0.3 ± 0.0c	0.5 ± 0.0b	1.6 ± 0.0a	0.7 ± 0.1b	1.9 ± 0.0a	1.9 ± 0.0a	1.1 ± 0.0b	2.3 ± 0.1a	2.1 ± 0.1a	1.6 ± 0.0b	2.5 ± 0.0a
(Z,E)-2,4-Nonadienal (138)*	81	0.2 ± 0.0c	0.9 ± 0.0b	1.8 ± 0.1a	0.9 ± 0.0c	3.8 ± 0.2b	5.2 ± 0.1a	1.7 ± 0.0b	4.6 ± 0.4a	5.2 ± 0.4a	2.8 ± 0.2b	4.6 ± 0.0a
(E,E)-2,4-Nonadienal (138)*	81	0.4 ± 0.0c	3.0 ± 0.2b	4.4 ± 0.3a	2.6 ± 0.0b	14.7 ± 0.5a	14.4 ± 0.7a	5.3 ± 0.1b	17.9 ± 1.8a	15.3 ± 1.2a	8.5 ± 0.7b	18.0 ± 0.1a
(Z,E)-2,4-Decadienal (152)*	81	5.3 ± 0.7c	13.0 ± 0.4b	72.0 ± 4.4a	36.8 ± 0.7c	77.3 ± 8.8b	132.3 ± 5.7a	73.9 ± 0.8b	111.1 ± 10.4a	93.6 ± 9.1 ab	116.9 ± 13.2a	118.4 ± 1.5a
(E,E)-2,4-Decadienal (152)*	81	16.6 ± 2.9c	47.1 ± 0.3b	265.3 ± 16.8a	118.4 ± 0.5c	301.6 ± 29.8b	520.5 ± 22.5a	241.9 ± 2.3b	450.9 ± 40.6a	391.5 ± 36.9a	400.4 ± 48.9b	507.2 ± 8.5a
(E,E)-2,4-Undecadienal (166)*	81	–	–	0.2 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.2 ± 0.0b	0.7 ± 0.1a	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.4 ± 0.0b	0.8 ± 0.1a	0.2 ± 0.0b	0.5 ± 0.0a
Total		24.4 ± 3.9c	68.0 ± 0.4b	354.9 ± 21.1a	164.5 ± 0.4c	407.2 ± 39.1b	687.1 ± 27.8a	330.9 ± 4.4b	594.6 ± 53.5a	516.4 ± 47.4a	540.8 ± 62.9b	657.1 ± 10.1a
<i>Oxygenated aldehydes</i>												
4-Oxo-(E)-2-pentenal (98)	83	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.3 ± 0.0b	0.4 ± 0.0a	0.3 ± 0.1c	0.8 ± 0.0a	0.5 ± 0.0b	0.3 ± 0.0b	1.3 ± 0.1a	0.5 ± 0.1b	0.3 ± 0.0b	1.0 ± 0.0a
4-Oxo-(E)-2-hexenal (112)	83	1.0 ± 0.1c	2.3 ± 0.0b	5.1 ± 0.1a	2.9 ± 0.1c	6.4 ± 0.1a	5.6 ± 0.2b	2.9 ± 1.2c	11.8 ± 0.0a	5.9 ± 0.2b	4.1 ± 0.0b	10.7 ± 0.2a
4-Oxo-nonanal (156)	43	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.3 ± 0.0b	2.5 ± 0.2a	0.3 ± 0.1b	0.5 ± 0.1b	9.0 ± 0.1a	0.4 ± 0.0b	0.5 ± 0.0b	9.8 ± 0.9a	0.7 ± 0.0a	0.7 ± 0.1a
4-Oxo-(E)-2-octenal (140)	55	0.6 ± 0.0c	1.6 ± 0.0b	6.3 ± 0.3a	3.0 ± 0.1c	7.2 ± 0.2b	10.9 ± 0.0a	5.4 ± 0.3b	8.0 ± 0.7a	7.7 ± 0.4a	7.8 ± 0.1a	7.2 ± 0.0a
4-Oxo-(E)-2-nonenal (154)	125	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.4 ± 0.0b	1.0 ± 0.1a	0.5 ± 0.0c	1.3 ± 0.2b	2.7 ± 0.1a	0.9 ± 0.0b	1.3 ± 0.2b	2.6 ± 0.2a	1.6 ± 0.3a	1.8 ± 0.1a
4,5-Epoxy-(E)-2-nonenal (154)	68	–	–	0.1 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.3 ± 0.0a	0.3 ± 0.0a	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.5 ± 0.1a	0.2 ± 0.0b	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.7 ± 0.0a
4,5-Epoxy-(E)-2-nonenal (154)	68	–	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.2 ± 0.0a	0.1 ± 0.0b	0.7 ± 0.1a	0.8 ± 0.0a	0.2 ± 0.0c	1.2 ± 0.1a	0.8 ± 0.1b	0.3 ± 0.1b	1.5 ± 0.0a
4,5-Epoxy-(E)-2-decenal (168)	68	–	0.3 ± 0.0b	2.2 ± 0.1a	0.4 ± 0.0c	3.8 ± 0.7b	7.0 ± 0.1a	0.9 ± 0.0b	7.7 ± 0.8a	6.5 ± 0.8a	2.2 ± 0.7b	10.5 ± 0.4a
4,5-Epoxy-(E)-2-decenal (168)*	68	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.8 ± 0.0b	5.4 ± 0.2a	0.9 ± 0.0c	10.4 ± 2.0b	17.2 ± 0.4a	2.4 ± 0.0b	21.1 ± 2.1a	16.7 ± 2.2a	6.0 ± 1.7b	28.8 ± 1.3a
4-Hidroxy-(E)-2-nonenal (156)	57	0.1 ± 0.0c	0.7 ± 0.0b	3.9 ± 0.1a	0.4 ± 0.1c	2.6 ± 0.4b	9.3 ± 0.2a	0.6 ± 0.1c	2.9 ± 0.1b	8.0 ± 0.8a	1.7 ± 0.5b	4.0 ± 0.2a
Total		2.2 ± 0.2c	6.8 ± 0.2b	27.1 ± 1.1a	8.8 ± 0.3c	34.0 ± 3.5b	63.1 ± 0.8a	14.0 ± 1.7b	56.3 ± 3.9a	58.7 ± 5.1a	24.8 ± 3.4b	66.7 ± 1.9a

Asterisked compounds were acquired commercially and used as standards for identification purposes. Abbreviations: 120VF: vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C; 120AF: atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C; 170AF: atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C; -: not detected.

In addition to the aforementioned compounds, some **oxygenated aldehydes** were formed during the different frying processes, as shown in Table 1. It can be observed that 4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenals were generated in the highest abundance, independently of the heating conditions. The evolution of these compounds over time was similar to that described for (*E*)-2-alkenals and 2,4-alkadienals. Under atmospheric conditions at 170 °C, a significantly higher and faster formation of oxygenated aldehydes was observed, with maximum abundances reached after 18 h of heating (see 170AF in Table 1), followed by a decrease. Furthermore, as expected, the formation of oxygenated aldehydes was closely related to the lower oxygen concentration inside the fryer. Thus, when comparing 120VF and 120AF, it was observed that, at any heating time, the abundance of all types of oxygenated aldehydes was consistently and significantly lower under vacuum frying conditions. Moreover, in contrast to what was observed in atmospheric frying (both at 120 °C and 170 °C), 4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-nonenals and 4,5-epoxy-(*E*)-2-decenal were not detected at all in the oil sample after the first heating cycle under vacuum frying. Therefore, these results demonstrate that lower temperature and restricted access to air significantly reduce the formation of oxygenated aldehydes. This finding is of considerable importance, since oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes have been related to several diseases, such as cancer, Alzheimer's, and Parkinson's, due to their geno- and cytotoxicity (Esterbauer et al., 1991; Guillén & Goicoechea, 2008).

Finally, it should be noted that studies on the profile of aldehydes generated under vacuum conditions are scarce, with only a few identified, and none of which include oxygenated α,β -unsaturated aldehydes (Belkova et al., 2018). In fact, in most studies, the presence of such compounds is assessed using the *p*-anisidine value (Crosa et al., 2014; Manzoor et al., 2022; Pandey et al., 2022), which provides a general measure of secondary oxidation products. To our knowledge, this is the first study to examine the headspace of sunflower oil under vacuum conditions, focusing on the evolution of a wide range of aldehydes.

3.3. Changes in the percentage of Total Polar Compounds (TPC) and viscosity

Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the TPC percentage through the heating process under the different conditions studied (120VF, 120AF and 170AF). The percentage of TPC gradually increased with time in the three experiments, although the formation rates differed between conditions. Specifically, 170AF samples reached 25% TPC after 30 h (formation rate of 0.64 % of TPC hour⁻¹), 120AF samples after 44 h

Fig. 6. Evolution of the percentage of Total Polar Compounds (% TPC) in sunflower oil submitted to vacuum-frying conditions at 120 °C (120VF -○-), atmospheric-frying conditions at 120 °C (120AF -Δ-) and atmospheric-frying conditions at 170 °C (170AF -x-). For the same heating time, non-significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between samples are asterisked (*) and grouped in dotted squares.

(formation rate of 0.45% of TPC hour⁻¹), and 120VF after 162 h of treatment, with the lowest formation rate (0.11 % of TPC hour⁻¹). These results are in line with those described in previous sections and also agree with the findings reported by other authors, who observed a lower percentage of TPC in oils used for vacuum frying experiments (with or without food) compared to those used for traditional atmospheric frying (with or without food) (Basuny et al., 2012; Crosa et al., 2014; Nateghi et al., 2018; Pandey et al., 2022).

The percentage variation in viscosity over time was also calculated in sunflower oil samples subjected to different frying conditions. Under 170AF, viscosity increased by 26.3% after 30 h, when 25% TPC was reached. In contrast, at the same time point, 120AF showed a viscosity increase of 17.1%, while 120VF exhibited the lowest value (3.1%). These results are consistent with those reported by other authors, who found that the low oxygen content and temperatures used during vacuum frying reduce the rate of polymerisation in the oil (Nateghi et al., 2018). However, it should be noted that the percentage change in viscosity at the end of the experiments at 120 °C (44 h in 120AF and 162 h in 120VF) was very similar to that at 170 °C (24.0% in 120AF and 24.9% in 120VF).

4. Conclusions

In view of the results obtained in the present study, it is evident that vacuum frying is an effective strategy to improve the oxidative stability of oils subjected to frying. Overall, the combination of low oxygen concentration in the headspace and the lower temperatures used under vacuum frying conditions significantly increases the oxidative stability of sunflower oil. In summary, it has been shown that the time of use of heated oils, legally established in Spain and other countries when the oil reaches 25% TPC, is achieved more than 5.5 times later under vacuum conditions, thus significantly prolonging the usability of the oil. This is consistent with the holistic process perspective provided by ¹H NMR and SPME-GC/MS. It has been shown that the main lipidic components of the oil, namely linoleic acyl groups, degrade at a significantly lower rate under vacuum frying conditions, thus preserving the nutritional value of the oil for a much longer period. In particular, the present study has described for the first time the formation of several oxygenated compounds in sunflower oil subjected to vacuum frying conditions. With the exception of primary oxidation products (monohydroperoxy-conjugated octadecadienoates), which do not accumulate at the temperatures used in conventional frying due to their instability, the generation of other oxygenated oxidation compounds under vacuum frying conditions is delayed compared to conventional frying, owing to the improved stability of the linoleic groups. Finally, it should be noted that the higher oxidative stability of the frying oil achieved by this technique is of great importance from a sustainability point of view. Not only does it help to maintain the nutritional and safety value of the oil for longer, but it also prolongs the use of the frying oil, thus minimising the volume of waste generated.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andrea Martínez-Yusta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ainhoa Ruiz-Aracama:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Jon Alberdi-Cedeño:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Notes

The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the

results.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2025.117507>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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